

COMPARISON OF PROPHYLACTIC PHENYLEPHRINE INFUSION VERSUS BOLUS REGIMENS ON MATERNAL HEMODYNAMICS DURING CESAREAN SECTION

Dr. Maryam Shoukat^{*1}, Dr. Sana Siddiq², Dr. Muhammed Ameer Hamzah³

^{*1}maryam.shoukat49@gmail.com

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Corresponding Author: *

Dr. Maryam Shoukat

Abstract

Objective: To compare mean systolic blood pressure for 45 minutes after giving spinal anesthesia between prophylactic phenylephrine group and bolus regimens in patients undergoing spinal anesthesia for cesarean section.

Study Design: Randomized Controlled Trial.

Place & Duration: Six months w.e.f. 06-06-2024 to 05-12-2024 at Department of Anesthesia, Hameed Latif Hospital, Lahore.

Methodology: After approval from the ethical review committee, 60 patients were randomly assigned to two groups. Baseline vitals, including systolic blood pressure, were recorded, and all patients received a 10 mL/kg normal saline bolus. Spinal anesthesia was administered with 12 mg of hyperbaric 0.75% bupivacaine. Group A received a prophylactic phenylephrine infusion, while Group B received phenylephrine bolus upon hypotension. Blood pressure was monitored at regular intervals. Data were analyzed using SPSS, with statistical significance set at $p \leq 0.05$.

Results: This study involved 60 participants with a mean maternal age of 27.05 years. Most participants were aged 18-30 years (65.0%), and 43.6% were in the >39-week gestational age range. The mean BMI was 25.82 kg/m², with 43.6% categorized as overweight or obese. Both groups were comparable at baseline. At 45 minutes, Group A had a significantly higher SBP than Group B, with differences observed across age, gestational age, and BMI subgroups, indicating better hemodynamic control in Group A.

Conclusion: The study demonstrated that prophylactic phenylephrine infusion maintained a more stable and higher systolic blood pressure compared to the bolus regimen at 45 minutes post-intervention. This finding suggests that a continuous infusion may offer better hemodynamic control during cesarean sections.

INTRODUCTION

The rate of cesarean-section deliveries in Pakistan stands at 22%, according to the 2017-2018 Pakistan Demographics and Health Survey.¹ This high rate makes anesthesia management a significant concern due to the physiological changes associated with pregnancy and the added complexities of a fetus or fetuses. The challenges posed to anesthesia providers in this context are substantial, as pregnancy-induced

physiological changes require careful consideration to ensure safe and effective anesthesia administration.^{2,3}

In the obstetric population, around 80% of patients undergoing cesarean section with spinal anesthesia develop hypotension without proper prophylactic measures.⁴ Pregnancy-associated changes, such as reduced sensitivity to endogenous vasoconstrictors

and an increased synthesis of vasodilators, make parturients more prone to sympathectomy. Severe hypotension can lead to adverse outcomes, including nausea, vomiting, and unpleasant feelings of impending doom, as well as fetal acidosis. As a result, timely and accurate management of hypotension is essential to ensure the safety of both mother and fetus.^{5,6,7}

Phenylephrine, a vasopressor, is commonly used to treat maternal hypotension and has proven effective in reducing complications such as nausea and vomiting. However, its use may also lead to maternal bradycardia.⁸ The current consensus, as stated by the Association of Anesthetists of Great Britain and Ireland (AAGBI) in 2018, recommends prophylactic phenylephrine infusion after intrathecal injection.⁹

Kumar et al. found that at 10 minutes post-spinal anesthesia, mean systolic blood pressure was significantly higher in the prophylactic phenylephrine infusion group (112.03 ± 14.6 mmHg) compared to the bolus group (100.5 ± 7.6 mmHg) (P = 0.0001).¹⁰ Singh et al. reported consistently higher systolic blood pressure in the infusion group at various time points, with significant differences (P < 0.001) until 18 minutes.

After 18 minutes, SBP values became comparable between the two groups until the 30-minute mark.¹¹ Although there is a lack of literature comparing prophylactic phenylephrine infusion regimen and bolus regimen, there are inconsistent results and this study sought to evaluate the outcomes of these two phenylephrine regimens in a local settings. The research will aid in the optimization of maternal hemodynamic management during CS by offering insights into the effectiveness of these regimens, which will help to understand which approach is better in terms of better patient outcomes.

METHODOLOGY

Following synopsis and ethical review, this randomized controlled trial was carried out at the Department of Anesthesia, Hameed Latif Hospital, Lahore. The objective of the study was to compare the effectiveness of prophylactic phenylephrine infusion and bolus phenylephrine use in the management of maternal hypotension at cesarean section under spinal anesthesia. The WHO sample size calculator was used to determine the sample size

based on the results of a past study. With a power of 80% and a 95% confidence interval, 30 patients were allocated to each of the two groups, totaling 60 participants.⁹ The study inclusion criteria included uncomplicated singleton pregnancy undergoing elective cesarean delivery and ASA I or II with the absence of known fetal abnormalities. Patient refusal, hypersensitivity to bupivacaine known, age below 18 years, and bleeding disorders were used as exclusion factors.

The study enrolled 60 patients who were randomly assigned to the two groups. Baseline vital signs, including systolic blood pressure, were recorded, and all patients were co-loaded with normal saline at 10 mL/kg. Spinal anesthesia was administered using a 25G Pencan needle at the L3-L4 space, with 12 mg of hyperbaric 0.75% bupivacaine. Following the procedure, patients were placed in the supine position with a 15-degree wedge under the right buttock. Group A received a continuous prophylactic phenylephrine infusion at 0.5 mcg/kg/min, while Group B was administered a 50 µg phenylephrine bolus upon hypotension. Blood pressure was monitored at regular intervals throughout the procedure, with readings taken every 2 minutes for the first 15 minutes, followed by 5-minute intervals for the next 15 minutes, and 10-minute intervals for the last 15 minutes. In cases of hypotension, epinephrine (5 mcg) was given if the heart rate was less than 75 beats per minute, or phenylephrine (50 mcg) if the heart rate exceeded 75 beats per minute. The number of boluses administered to maintain mean arterial pressure was also recorded. Data analysis was performed using SPSS version 21. Continuous variables were done using descriptive statistics. Independent sample t-tests were used to compare groups. Chi-square tests were used to analyze categorical variables. The p-value of 0.05 or less was taken to be statistically significant. The data were stratified on the basis of maternal age, BMI and gestational age. Independent sample t-tests were used to make post stratification comparisons.

RESULTS

Table I shows that mean maternal age was 27.05 ± 5.67 years, with 65.0% of participants falling within the 18-30 years age range, and 35.0% in the 31-40 years range. The mean gestational age was 38.70 ±

1.17 weeks, with 19.3% of participants at 38-39 weeks and 43.6% at >39 weeks. Mean BMI was 25.82 ± 2.63 , where 19.3% of participants had normal weight and 43.6% as overweight/obese. Regarding ASA status, 81.7% were classified as ASA-I and 18.3% as ASA-II. The baseline systolic blood pressure (SBP) was 116.13 ± 4.27 mmHg. Both groups were balanced statistically with regard to baseline variables ($p > 0.05$), as given in Table II. At

45 minutes, Group A ($n=30$) had a significantly higher SBP of 116.13 ± 8.08 mmHg compared to Group B ($n=30$), which had a SBP of 106.10 ± 7.41 mmHg ($p=0.000$) as shown in Table III. Table IV shows the comparison of mean SBP at 45 minutes between Group A and Group B, stratified by age, gestational age, and BMI. Group A consistently had a significantly higher SBP than Group B across all subgroups ($p \leq 0.05$).

Table I: Sociodemographic Profile of Cesarean Section Patients

Characteristics	(n=60)
Maternal Age (years)	27.05±5.67
• 18-30	91 (65.0%)
• 31-40	49 (35.0%)
Gestational Age	38.70±1.17
• 38-39 weeks	27 (19.3%)
• >39 week	61 (43.6%)
BMI (kg/m ²)	25.82±2.63
• Normal Weight	27 (19.3%)
• Overweight / Obese	61 (43.6%)
ASA Status	
• ASA-I	49 (81.7%)
• ASA-II	11 (18.3%)
SBP (baseline) mmHg	116.13±4.27

Table II: Baseline Profile Comparison Across Groups

Characteristics	Group A (n=30)	Group B (n=30)	p-value
Maternal Age (years)	26.80±5.68	27.30±5.74	0.736
• 18-30 years	20 (66.7%)	18 (60.0%)	0.592
• 31-40 years	10 (33.3%)	12 (40.0%)	
Gestational Age (weeks)	38.73±1.08	38.67±1.27	0.827
• 38-39 weeks	14 (46.7%)	15 (50.0%)	0.796
• >39 week	16 (53.3%)	15 (50.0%)	
BMI (kg/m ²)	26.08±2.54	25.56±2.73	0.800
• Normal Weight	11 (36.7%)	14 (46.7%)	0.432
• Overweight / Obese	19 (63.3%)	16 (53.3%)	
ASA Status			
• ASA-I	25 (83.3%)	24 (80.0%)	0.739
• ASA-II	5 (16.7%)	6 (20.0%)	
SBP (baseline) mmHg	116.33±4.02	115.93±4.56	0.720

Table III: Comparison of Mean SBP between the Groups at 45 Minutes Interval

Systolic Blood Pressure	Group A	Group B	p-value
At 45 Minutes Interval	116.13±8.08	106.10±7.41	0.000

Table IV: Comparison of Mean SBP at 45 Minutes Interval between the Group Stratified for Age, Gestational Age and BMI

Group	Subgroups	Group A	Group B	p-value
Age	18-30 years	115.25±7.89	105.22±7.03	0.000
	31-40 years	117.90±8.57	107.42±8.08	.008
Gestational Age	38-39 weeks	118.43±7.95	104.87±8.37	0.000
	>39 week	114.13±7.88	107.33±6.36	0.014
BMI	Normal Weight	115.09±9.53	106.79±7.91	0.026
	Overweight / Obese	116.74±7.32	105.50±7.16	0.000
ASA	ASA-I	116.40±8.20	106.88±7.62	0.000
	ASA-II	114.80±8.17	103.00±6.10	0.031

DISCUSSION

The increasing number of cesarean sections (CS) has highlighted the need for effective management of maternal hemodynamics during surgery.¹²⁻¹⁴ However, there is limited literature comparing prophylactic phenylephrine infusion versus bolus regimens, with few interventions and some contradictory findings.^{10,11} Given the lack of local studies, this research was planned to investigate the effects of these regimens on maternal hemodynamics during CS in a local population, aiming to provide more definitive conclusions on their effectiveness. The mean maternal age in this study was 27.05±5.67 years that are very close to mean age of 27.17±3.36 years reported by Kumar et al. in India.¹⁰ Two other Indian studies reported mean age of the participants as 25.39±2.8 years and 24.02±2.69 years by Choudhary et al. and Sing et al., respectively.^{15,11} The mean gestational age was 38.70±1.17 weeks in this study, which is similar to mean gestational age of 38.4±0.53 weeks reported by Kumar et al. in India and 38.4±2.2 weeks reported by Nikooseresht et al. in Iran.^{10,16} Mean BMI was 25.82 ± 2.63 kg/m², which is a little lower than reported by Sing et al. as 27.72±3.15. Regarding ASA status, 81.7% were classified as ASA-I and 18.3% as ASA-II in this study. Previously, Kumar et al. reported ASA-I status in 83.3% of their study population.¹⁰

In this study, SBP was 116.13 ± 4.27 mmHg. Kumar et al. reported baseline SBP of 123.5±9.3 mmHg, Nikooseresht et al. reported it 120.03±8.69 mmHg and Kannan et al. reported it 116.4 mmHg.^{16,17}

In this study, at 45 minutes, Group A had a significantly higher SBP of 116.13 ± 8.08 mmHg compared to Group B, which had a SBP of 106.10 ± 7.41 mmHg (p=0.000). Previously conducted similar studies have observed SBP at various time intervals. Kumar et al. reported that Group A's systolic blood pressure (SBP) gradually declined from 123.5 ± 9.3 mmHg at baseline (T0) to 112.03 ± 14.6 mmHg at 10 minutes (T10).¹⁰ Group B showed a more significant decrease, from 120.73 ± 11.1 mmHg at T0 to 100.5 ± 7.6 mmHg at T10. Statistically significant differences were observed at several time points (T1-T10), with p-values ranging from 0.003 to 0.0001, indicating a more stable SBP in Group A compared to Group B. They concluded that SBP was significantly higher over time in group A. Choudhary et al. observed that in the bolus infusion group, 44 patients experienced a decline of over 20% in systolic blood pressure (SBP) from baseline. The mean decrease in SBP for this group was -28.06 ± 5.3 mmHg, whereas in the prophylactic group, the mean decrease was much smaller, at -0.44 ± 4.3 mmHg.¹⁵ Singh et al. found that baseline and zero-minute systolic blood pressure (SBP) were comparable between the groups (P>0.05). However, during the

intergroup comparison, the mean SBP was consistently higher in the prophylactic infusion group compared to the bolus group at the 6th, 9th, 12th, 15th, and 18th minutes, with statistically significant differences ($P < 0.001$). After 18 minutes, SBP values became comparable between the two groups until the 30-minute mark.¹¹ Nikooseresht et al. reported that prophylactic infusion showed a significantly higher SBP than prophylactic bolus at 2 and 7 minutes. There were no significant differences at other time points.¹⁶ Kannan et al. concluded that the bolus group had no instances of increased SBP ($>20\%$), while the prophylactic infusion group had 12.5%. The bolus group also had more cases of decreased SBP ($>20\%$) compared to the prophylactic infusion group (5.0% vs. 0.0%). Both groups showed $<20\%$ SBP changes in most cases. Significant differences in SBP trends were observed, with the bolus group showing a drop and the prophylactic infusion group showing a rise at the three-minute interval ($p = 0.000$).¹⁷

This study's strength lies in its novel approach to comparing prophylactic phenylephrine infusion and bolus regimens in managing maternal hemodynamics during cesarean sections, filling a gap in local research. However, some of the limitations are relatively smaller sample size and lack of long-term follow-up. Future studies should focus on larger, multi-center trials with diverse populations, exploring additional maternal and fetal outcomes to further validate the effectiveness of these interventions in different settings and improve clinical practices in managing CS-related hemodynamic changes.

CONCLUSION

The study demonstrated that prophylactic phenylephrine infusion maintained a more stable and higher systolic blood pressure compared to the bolus regimen at 45 minutes post-intervention. This finding suggests that a continuous infusion may offer better hemodynamic control during cesarean sections, reducing the risk of hypotension-related complications, especially across various maternal subgroups based on age, gestational age, and BMI.

Authors Contribution

Author 1

Substantial contributions to study design, acquisition of data

Analysis & Interpretation of Data, Manuscript writing

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

Author 2 & 3

Substantial contributions to concept, study design

Data Analysis, Manuscript writing, Critical Review

Has given final approval of the version to be published

Agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved

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